

Some properties of primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group

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Abstract: The concept of interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group is extended by introducing primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group using this concept primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group is defined. We also proved some properties of the above are established.

Keywords: Intuitionistic fuzzy set, Interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set, Primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ever since an introduction of fuzzy set by L.A.Zadeh [8], the fuzzy concept has invaded almost all branches of mathematics. The concept of IFS and IVIFS was introduced by K.T.Atanassov[1,2] as a generalization of the notion of fuzzy set. K.Chakrabarthy, R.Biswas and S.Nanda [4] discussed union and intersection of IFS. G.Prasannavengeteswari, K.Gunasekaran and .S.Nandakumar [5] introduced the definition of Primary Interval-Valued Intuitionistic Fuzzy M Group (PIVIFMG). In this paper, Some Properties of Primary interval-valued Intuitionistic Fuzzy M Group discussed.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition

An IVIFS A over the set E is of the form $A = \{ \langle p, M_A(p), N_A(p) \rangle | p \in E \}$, where $M_A(p) \subset [0,1]$ and $N_A(p) \subset [0,1]$ are intervals and $\sup M_A(p) + \sup N_A(p) \leq 1$, for every $p \in E$, we note IVIFS A as $A = \{ \langle p, [inf M_A(p), sup M_A(p)], [inf N_A(p), sup N_A(p)] \rangle | p \in E \}$, we write $[inf M_A(p), sup M_A(p)] = [\omega_A^-(p), \omega_A^+(p)]$ and $[inf N_A(p), sup N_A(p)] = [\varpi_A^-(p), \varpi_A^+(p)]$, where $\omega_A^+(p), \varpi_A^+(p), \omega_A^-(p), \varpi_A^-(p)$ are functions from E into $[0,1]$ and $\forall p \in E$, $(\omega_A^-(p) \leq \omega_A^+(p), \varpi_A^-(p) \leq \varpi_A^+(p), \omega_A^+(p) + \varpi_A^+(p) \leq 1)$. Here ω_A^+ and ω_A^- are degree of positive and negative members, ϖ_A^+ and ϖ_A^- degree of positive and negative non-members. we note $\omega_A^-(p) = inf M_A(p), \omega_A^+(p) = sup M_A(p), \varpi_A^-(p) = inf N_A(p), \varpi_A^+(p) = sup N_A(p)$.

Definition

Let G be a M group and A be an interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy subgroup of G, then A is called a PIVIFMG. If for all $p, q \in G$ and $m \in M$, then either $\omega_A^+(mpq) \leq \omega_A^+(p^x)$ and $\varpi_A^+(mpq) \geq \varpi_A^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$ or else $\omega_A^+(mpq) \leq \omega_A^+(q^y)$ and $\varpi_A^+(mpq) \geq \varpi_A^+(q^y)$, for some $y \in Z_+$ and either $\omega_A^-(mpq) \geq \omega_A^-(p^x)$ and $\varpi_A^-(mpq) \leq \varpi_A^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$ or else $\omega_A^-(mpq) \geq \omega_A^-(q^y)$ and $\varpi_A^-(mpq) \leq \varpi_A^-(q^y)$, for some $y \in Z_+$.

Some Properties of primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group

Theorem: 1

If R, S and T are primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group, then $R \cup (S \cap T) = (R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)$ is also a primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^+(mpq) &= \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_{S \cap T}^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \min(\omega_S^+(mpq), \omega_T^+(mpq))) \\
 &= \max(\sup M_R(mpq), \min(\sup M_S(mpq), \sup M_T(mpq))) \\
 &\leq \max(\sup M_R(p^x), \min(\sup M_S(p^x), \sup M_T(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \min(\omega_S^+(p^x), \omega_T^+(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x)), \max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_T^+(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\omega_{R \cup S}^+(p^x), \omega_{R \cup T}^+(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^+(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^+(mpq) \leq \omega_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^+(mpq) &= \min(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_{S \cap T}^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \max(\varpi_S^+(mpq), \varpi_T^+(mpq))) \\
 &= \min(\sup N_R(mpq), \max(\sup N_S(mpq), \sup N_T(mpq))) \\
 &\geq \min(\sup N_R(p^x), \max(\sup N_S(p^x), \sup N_T(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \max(\varpi_S^+(p^x), \varpi_T^+(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\min(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \varpi_S^+(p^x)), \min(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \varpi_T^+(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_{R \cup S}^+(p^x), \varpi_{R \cup T}^+(p^x)) \\
 &= \varpi_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^+(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^+(mpq) \geq \varpi_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^-(mpq) &= \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_{S \cap T}^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \max(\omega_S^-(mpq), \omega_T^-(mpq))) \\
 &= \min(\inf M_R(mpq), \max(\inf M_S(mpq), \inf M_T(mpq))) \\
 &\geq \min(\inf M_R(p^x), \max(\inf M_S(p^x), \inf M_T(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \max(\omega_S^-(p^x), \omega_T^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x)), \min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_T^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\omega_{R \cup S}^-(p^x), \omega_{R \cup T}^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^-(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^-(mpq) \geq \omega_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^-(mpq) &= \max(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_{S \cap T}^-(mpq)) \\ &= \max(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \min(\varpi_S^-(mpq), \varpi_T^-(mpq))) \\ &= \max(\inf N_R(mpq), \min(\inf N_S(mpq), \inf N_T(mpq))) \\ &\leq \max(\inf N_R(p^x), \min(\inf N_S(p^x), \inf N_T(p^x))) \\ &= \max(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \min(\varpi_S^-(p^x), \varpi_T^-(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\max(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_S^-(p^x)), \max(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_T^-(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\varpi_{R \cup S}^-(p^x), \varpi_{R \cup T}^-(p^x)) \\ &= \varpi_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^-(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cup (S \cap T)}^-(mpq) \leq \varpi_{(R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

Therefore $R \cup (S \cap T) = (R \cup S) \cap (R \cup T)$ is also a primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Theorem: 2

If R, S and T are primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group, then

$R \cap (S \cup T) = (R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)$ is also a primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^+(mpq) &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_{S \cup T}^+(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \max(\omega_S^+(mpq), \omega_T^+(mpq))) \\ &= \min(\sup M_R(mpq), \max(\sup M_S(mpq), \sup M_T(mpq))) \\ &\leq \min(\sup M_R(p^x), \max(\sup M_S(p^x), \sup M_T(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \max(\omega_S^+(p^x), \omega_T^+(p^x))) \\ &= \max(\min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x)), \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_T^+(p^x))) \\ &= \max(\omega_{R \cap S}^+(p^x), \omega_{R \cap T}^+(p^x)) \\ &= \omega_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^+(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^+(mpq) \leq \omega_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^+(mpq) &= \max(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_{S \cup T}^+(mpq)) \\ &= \max(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \min(\varpi_S^+(mpq), \varpi_T^+(mpq))) \\ &= \max(\sup N_R(mpq), \min(\sup N_S(mpq), \sup N_T(mpq))) \\ &\geq \max(\sup N_R(p^x), \min(\sup N_S(p^x), \sup N_T(p^x))) \\ &= \max(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \min(\varpi_S^+(p^x), \varpi_T^+(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\max(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \varpi_S^+(p^x)), \max(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \varpi_T^+(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\varpi_{R \cap S}^+(p^x), \varpi_{R \cap T}^+(p^x)) \\ &= \varpi_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^+(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^+(mpq) \geq \varpi_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^-(mpq) &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_{S \cup T}^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \min(\omega_S^-(mpq), \omega_T^-(mpq))) \\
 &= \max(\inf M_R(mpq), \min(\inf M_S(mpq), \inf M_T(mpq))) \\
 &\geq \max(\inf M_R(p^x), \min(\inf M_S(p^x), \inf M_T(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \min(\omega_S^-(p^x), \omega_T^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x)), \max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_T^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\omega_{R \cap S}^-(p^x), \omega_{R \cap T}^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^-(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^-(mpq) \geq \varpi_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^-(mpq) &= \min(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_{S \cup T}^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \max(\varpi_S^-(mpq), \varpi_T^-(mpq))) \\
 &= \min(\inf N_R(mpq), \max(\inf N_S(mpq), \inf N_T(mpq))) \\
 &\leq \min(\inf N_R(p^x), \max(\inf N_S(p^x), \inf N_T(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \max(\varpi_S^-(p^x), \varpi_T^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\min(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_S^-(p^x)), \min(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_T^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_{R \cap S}^-(p^x), \varpi_{R \cap T}^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \varpi_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^-(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cap (S \cup T)}^-(mpq) \leq \varpi_{(R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

Therefore $R \cap (S \cup T) = (R \cap S) \cup (R \cap T)$ is also a primary interval- valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Theorem: 3

If R and S are primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group, then $R \cup (R \cap S) = R$ is also a primary interval- valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^+(mpq) &= \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_{R \cap S}^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_S^+(mpq))) \\
 &= \max(\sup M_R(mpq), \min(\sup M_R(mpq), \sup M_S(mpq))) \\
 &\leq \max(\sup M_R(p^x), \min(\sup M_R(p^x), \sup M_S(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_R^+(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^+(mpq) \leq \omega_R^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^+(mpq) &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_{R \cap S}^+(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_S^+(mpq))) \\ &= \min(\sup N_R(mpq), \max(\sup N_R(mpq), \sup N_S(mpq))) \\ &\geq \min(\sup N_R(p^x), \max(\sup N_R(p^x), \sup N_S(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x)) \\ &= \omega_R^+(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\nu_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^+(mpq) \geq \omega_R^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^-(mpq) &= \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_{R \cap S}^-(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_S^-(mpq))) \\ &= \min(\inf M_R(mpq), \max(\inf M_R(mpq), \inf M_S(mpq))) \\ &\geq \min(\inf M_R(p^x), \max(\inf M_R(p^x), \inf M_S(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x))) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x)) \\ &= \omega_R^-(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^-(mpq) \geq \omega_R^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^-(mpq) &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_{R \cap S}^-(mpq)) \\ &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_S^-(mpq))) \\ &= \max(\inf N_R(mpq), \min(\inf N_R(mpq), \inf N_S(mpq))) \\ &\leq \max(\inf N_R(p^x), \min(\inf N_R(p^x), \inf N_S(p^x))) \\ &= \max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x))) \\ &= \max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x)) \\ &= \omega_R^-(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cup (R \cap S)}^-(mpq) \leq \omega_R^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

Therefore $R \cup (R \cap S) = R$ is also a primary interval- valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Theorem: 4

If R and S are primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group, then $R \cap (R \cup S) = R$ is also a primary interval- valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^+(mpq) &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_{R \cup S}^+(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_S^+(mpq))) \\ &= \min(\sup M_R(mpq), \max(\sup M_R(mpq), \sup M_S(mpq))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \min(\sup M_R(p^x), \max(\sup M_R(p^x), \sup M_S(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x))) \\
 &= \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_R^+(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^+(mpq) \leq \omega_R^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^+(mpq) &= \max(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_{R \cup S}^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \min(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_S^+(mpq))) \\
 &= \max(\sup N_R(mpq), \min(\sup N_R(mpq), \sup N_S(mpq))) \\
 &\geq \max(\sup N_R(p^x), \min(\sup N_R(p^x), \sup N_S(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \min(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \varpi_S^+(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_A^+(p^x), \varpi_B^+(p^x)) \\
 &= \varpi_R^+(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^+(mpq) \geq \varpi_R^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^-(mpq) &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_{R \cup S}^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_S^-(mpq))) \\
 &= \max(\inf M_R(mpq), \min(\inf M_R(mpq), \inf M_S(mpq))) \\
 &\geq \max(\inf M_R(p^x), \min(\inf M_R(p^x), \inf M_S(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_R^-(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\mu_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^-(mpq) \geq \omega_R^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^-(mpq) &= \min(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_{R \cup S}^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \max(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_S^-(mpq))) \\
 &= \max(\inf N_R(mpq), \min(\inf N_R(mpq), \inf N_S(mpq))) \\
 &\leq \max(\inf N_R(p^x), \min(\inf N_R(p^x), \inf N_S(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \min(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_S^-(p^x))) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_S^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \varpi_R^-(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cap (R \cup S)}^-(mpq) \leq \varpi_R^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

Therefore $R \cap (R \cup S) = R$ is also a primary interval- valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Theorem: 5

If R and S are primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group, then $\overline{R} \cap \overline{S} = \overline{R \cup S}$ is also a primary interval- valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Proof:

Let R and S be two primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group of G .

Consider $p, q \in R \cap S$ and $m \in M$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cap S}^+(mpq) &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_S^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_S^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\sup N_R(mpq), \sup N_S(mpq)) \\
 &\leq \min(\sup N_R(p^x), \sup N_S(p^x)) \\
 &= \min(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \varpi_S^+(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_{R \cup S}^+(p^x) \\
 &= \omega_{R \cup S}^+(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cap S}^+(mpq) \leq \omega_{R \cup S}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cap S}^+(mpq) &= \max(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_S^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_S^+(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\sup M_R(mpq), \sup M_S(mpq)) \\
 &\geq \max(\sup M_R(p^x), \sup M_S(p^x)) \\
 &= \max(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_{R \cup S}^+(p^x) \\
 &= \varpi_{R \cup S}^+(p^x).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{R \cap S}^+(mpq) \geq \varpi_{R \cup S}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \omega_{R \cap S}^-(mpq) &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_S^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_S^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \max(\inf N_R(mpq), \inf N_S(mpq)) \\
 &\geq \max(\inf N_R(p^x), \inf N_S(p^x)) \\
 &= \max(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_S^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \varpi_{R \cup S}^-(p^x) \\
 &= \omega_{R \cup S}^-(p^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{R \cap S}^-(mpq) \geq \omega_{R \cup S}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Consider } \varpi_{R \cap S}^-(mpq) &= \min(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_S^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_S^-(mpq)) \\
 &= \min(\inf M_R(mpq), \inf M_S(mpq)) \\
 &\leq \min(\inf M_R(p^x), \inf M_S(p^x)) \\
 &= \min(\omega_R^-(p^x), \omega_S^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_{R \cup S}^-(p^x) \\
 &= \varpi_{R \cup S}^-(p^x).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{\overline{R \cap S}}^-(mpq) \leq \varpi_{\overline{R \cup S}}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

Therefore, $\overline{R \cap S} = \overline{R \cup S}$ is a primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group of G . \square

Theorem: 6

If R and S are primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group, then $\overline{R \cup S} = \overline{R \cap S}$ is also a primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group.

Proof:

Let R and S be two primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group of G .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \omega_{\overline{R \cup S}}^+(mpq) &= \max(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_S^+(mpq)) \\ &= \max(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_S^+(mpq)) \\ &= \max(\sup N_R(mpq), \sup N_S(mpq)) \\ &\leq \max(\sup N_R(p^x), \sup N_S(p^x)) \\ &= \max(\varpi_R^+(p^x), \varpi_S^+(p^x)) \\ &= \varpi_{R \cap S}^+(p^x) \\ &= \omega_{\overline{R \cap S}}^+(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{\overline{R \cup S}}^+(mpq) \leq \omega_{\overline{R \cap S}}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \varpi_{\overline{R \cup S}}^+(mpq) &= \min(\varpi_R^+(mpq), \varpi_S^+(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(mpq), \omega_S^+(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\sup M_R(mpq), \sup M_S(mpq)) \\ &\geq \min(\sup M_R(p^x), \sup M_S(p^x)) \\ &= \min(\omega_R^+(p^x), \omega_S^+(p^x)) \\ &= \omega_{R \cap S}^+(p^x) \\ &= \varpi_{\overline{R \cap S}}^+(p^x). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\varpi_{\overline{R \cup S}}^+(mpq) \geq \varpi_{\overline{R \cap S}}^+(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \omega_{\overline{R \cup S}}^-(mpq) &= \min(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_S^-(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_S^-(mpq)) \\ &= \min(\inf N_R(mpq), \inf N_S(mpq)) \\ &\geq \min(\inf N_R(p^x), \inf N_S(p^x)) \\ &= \min(\varpi_R^-(p^x), \varpi_S^-(p^x)) \\ &= \varpi_{R \cap S}^-(p^x) \\ &= \omega_{\overline{R \cap S}}^-(p^x) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{\overline{R \cup S}}^-(mpq) \geq \omega_{\overline{R \cap S}}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Consider } \varpi_{\overline{R \cup S}}^-(mpq) &= \max(\varpi_R^-(mpq), \varpi_S^-(mpq)) \\ &= \max(\omega_R^-(mpq), \omega_S^-(mpq)) \\ &= \max(\inf M_R(mpq), \inf M_S(mpq)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \max(\inf M_R(p^x), \inf M_S(p^x)) \\
 &= \max(\omega_{\bar{R}}^-(p^x), \omega_{\bar{S}}^-(p^x)) \\
 &= \omega_{\bar{R} \cap \bar{S}}^-(p^x) \\
 &= \omega_{\overline{\bar{R} \cup \bar{S}}}^-(p^x).
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\omega_{\overline{\bar{R} \cup \bar{S}}}^-(mpq) \leq \omega_{\overline{\bar{R} \cap \bar{S}}}^-(p^x)$, for some $x \in Z_+$

Therefore $\overline{\bar{R} \cup \bar{S}} = \overline{\bar{R} \cap \bar{S}}$ is a primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group of G .

3. CONCLUSION

In this paper the main idea of primary interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy M group is a new algebraic structures of fuzzy algebra and it is used through the some properties of the above. We believe that our ideas can also applied for other algebraic system.

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